

نبی صلی اللہ علیہ وسلم کی مکی اور مدنی زندگی کا تقابلی جائزہ

A Comparative Study of Makki And Madni Eras of The Life of Holy Prophet (SAW)

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Abstract

Prophet Muhammad (SAW) is the most influential figure in the entire history of mankind who reformed the most ignorant, uncivilized, brutal warrior and violent assassin Arab into civilized, peaceful and men of knowledge and wisdom in a short span of time (almost 23 years). Accustomed to idolatry were transformed into custodian of Tauheed and got uniformed as the beeds of neckless. The world's famous writer Micheal H. Hart has categorized the hundred most successful men according to the level of their prosperity in his most famous book "The Hundred". Despite of being a Christian, he has mentioned the name of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) at the top and Prophet Esa (AS) as third in the human history and he himself depicts the reason to keep Prophet Muhammad (SAW) on the top by saying that: "He was the only man in history who was supremely successful on both the religious and secular levels." (Pg: 3) While evaluating the profound life of Prophet Muhammad (SAW), two spans of time are found; Makki era and Madni era. The strategies and activities of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) appear differently in both of the eras for implementation of Allah's word and transformation of the mankind. The paper aims to describe the transformation of the policies of Prophat Muhammad (SAW) according to the need of time from Makki era to Madni Era. It elaborates how Prophet Muhammad (SAW) kept on changing his preaching strategies as well as social and political activities while keeping in view the conditions and circumstances in both of the eras. Moreover the paper also aims to highlight His dimensions in both of the eras in order to evaluate how He brought such a great revolution in such a short span of time.

Keywords: Prophet Muhammad (SAW), Makki era, Madni era. Comparative Study, Arabs into civilized

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